

INTERNALIZATION OF CUSTOM LAW IN CRIMINAL LAW FOR THE SAKE OF CREATING CERTAINTY LIVING LAW

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Abstract

Customary law is a form of living law that contains cultural values inherited from regional ancestors in Indonesia. Indigenous peoples are like flesh on the body in Indonesian society and their existence must be respected, and the internalization of customary law into criminal law is a form of respect for indigenous peoples. However, the fact is that several parts of the implementation of customary law in Indonesia still generate a lot of polemics because they conflict with Indonesian national law. What's more, customary law is unwritten law and it is very difficult to provide legal certainty to the community and it is necessary to apply the principle of legality to provide this certainty. The application of the principle of legality is a powerful way to avoid arbitrary or deviant actions that occur from actions based on customary law. In addition to applying the legality principle, a harmonization process is also needed to sort out which implementation of customary law conflicts with national law. After the application of the legality principle and the harmonization process, there is a need for a new implementation in the form of regulatory measures in balancing customary values and national legal values in creating justice.

Keywords: Customary Law; Criminal law; Legality Principle.

A. INTRODUCTION

1. Background

The 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia contains Article 18B paragraph (2) which explains that,

"The state respects and respects customary law communities and traditional rights as long as they are still alive and in accordance with the development of society and the principles of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, which are regulated in law."

Law is a rule born from society and this is closely related to the existence of living law (customary law) as the shaper of the applicable law in Indonesia.¹

Indonesian law must be able to have a goal that can provide welfare to the people. Gustav Radbruch stated in his book entitled "*einführung in die rechtswissenschaften*" that law must have 3 (three) basic values as its goal, namely: (1) Justice (*Gerechtigkeit*); (2) Benefits (*Zweckmässigkeit*); and (3) Legal Certainty (*Rechtssicherheit*).² The three basic values in the theory of legal objectives put forward by Gustav Radbruch will provide all the elements needed by society for the law itself, specifically for customary law. Matters that conflict or do not apply can be more harmonized with the theory of legal objectives put forward by Gustav Radbruch.³ Unwritten law cannot maximize the purpose of the law for the welfare of the people.

Customary law has a very strong presence in Indonesia, bearing in mind that Indonesia is a multicultural country with a wide variety of ethnic groups and customs as well as existence. Indigenous peoples are like flesh on the body in Indonesian society and must be respected. Implicitly, the state recognizes the existence of customary law that develops in every region in Indonesia. However, the fact is that the implementation of customary law in Indonesia still raises various polemics, one of which is because it

¹ Tim Lindsey, Simon Butt, *Indonesian Law*: Oxford University Press, 2018.

² Mario Julyano, Aditya Yuli Sulistyawan, "Pemahaman Terhadap Asas Kepastian Hukum Melalui Konstruksi Penalaran Positivisme Hukum", *Jurnal Mengenai Dasar-Dasar Pemikiran Hukum: Filsafat dan Ilmu Hukum* 1, No. 01 (Juli 2019)

³ Sonny Pungus, "Teori Tujuan Hukum". <http://sonny-tobelo.com/2010/10/teori-tujuan-hukum-gustav-radbruch-dan.html> (accessed November 5, 2022)

conflicts with Indonesian national law. Moreover, customary law as unwritten law is very difficult to provide legal certainty to the community. The absence of *lex certa* and *lex stricta* in customary law, makes customary law less assertive in responding to a phenomenon.

Internalization of customary law in Indonesian national law is one of the keys in mediating and resolving problems in terms of conflict between customary law and written law in Indonesia. This internalization aims to be able to provide legal certainty through the application of the principle of legality to customary law so that it does not conflict with Indonesian written law. Referring to Article 18B paragraph (2) of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, that in essence customary law may not conflict with the laws in force in Indonesia. In fact, respecting customary law does not make the state subject to customary law but states that the state allows the existence of customary law as a form of preservation and recognition of local customary culture in Indonesia.

The legality principle regulated in Article 1 paragraph (1) of Indonesian Law Number 1 of 2023 concerning The Criminal Code ("Latest Indonesian Criminal Code") stipulates,

"No act may be subject to criminal sanctions and/or action except under the force of criminal regulations in existing laws and regulations before the act is committed."

Moreover, what is written in Article 2 paragraph (1) of the new Criminal Code stipulates that,

"The provisions referred to in Article 1 paragraph (1) do not reduce the validity of the law that lives in society which determines that a person should be punished even though the act is not regulated in this law."⁴

The sentence "Not regulated in this law" refers to Article 2 paragraph (2) of the new Criminal Code,

"The law that lives in society as referred to in the paragraph applies in the place where the law lives and as long as it is not regulated in this law and is in accordance with the values contained in Pancasila, the 1945 Constitution of the

⁴ Member of the NasDem Party Fraction in the House of Representatives of the Republic of Indonesia. "Academic Text of Draft Law on Indigenous Peoples" <https://www.dpr.go.id/dokakd/kode/RJ2-20200226-051940-2495.pdf>. (accessed November 4, 2022)

Republic of Indonesia, human rights and generally recognized principles of law. civilized society.”⁵

The living law hereinafter referred to living law refers to a custom that exists in society. This customary law generally originates from what applies in an indigenous community. Islamic law which can be interpreted as living law has also been applied in several customary laws in customary law communities. From this, *living law* leaned more towards customary law which has given habits to multicultural Indonesian society.⁶

Even though each customary law is different in each region, there are overall similarities to each customary law, namely regarding the issue of discrimination. Customary law does not tolerate any element of accident and does not see an act of violation or crime as applied to criminal law which can tolerate an act of unintentional or self-defense.⁷ We can see this together from the case that occurred in Sumba where there was a small accident that caused injury to the victim. The perpetrators acknowledged that their actions were unintentional, but local customs punished the perpetrators with the same punishment as those caused on purpose. Perpetrators who do not agree with the sanctions obtained refuse to pay the fines of these sanctions. The customary law community who heard about this stated that they would carry out a war with the perpetrator's customary law community if the perpetrator did not pay a fine. Fortunately the local regional police were willing to pay off some of the perpetrators' fines, so that the customary war did not occur.⁸ This case example is clear evidence of the existence of injustice in the application of customary law which must be straightened out in order to create justice in it.

In reality, no law is perfect because justice is a subjective trait, which means it cannot be generalized to everyone.⁹ Justice can be viewed differently by everyone and very often this fair view is in conflict with Indonesian national law. One clear example is the case in the border area between the Inner and Outer Baduy. There was burning of four motorbikes carried out by the Baduy Dalam community. The burning was carried

⁵ Article 2 of the Criminal Code

⁶ The National Legal Development Agency, Ministry of Law and Human Rights of the Republic of Indonesia. "Draft Academic Documents on the Draft Law Concerning the Criminal Code (KUHP)" <https://www.dpr.go.id/dokakd/kode/RJ1-20181127-110919-8068.pdf>. (accessed November 4, 2022)

⁷ Tim Lindsey, Helen Pausacker, *Crime and Punishment in Indonesia*: Routledge, 2020.

⁸ Agus Budiarto, Rizky Karo Karo, "Marapu Customary Law Reconstruction Through The Establishment Of Regional Regulations As An Attempt Of Human Rights Protection Against The Native Sumba Society", *Jurnal Multicultural Education* (2021), 201-202

⁹ Agus Santoso, *Hukum, Moral, Dan Keadilan: Sebuah Kajian Filsafat Hukum*. Jakarta: Kencana, 2015.

out by the Baduy Dalam community because they did not like foreign culture entering the Baduy Dalam area.¹⁰ It is necessary to ensure that the actions of indigenous peoples are correct as actions of applicable customary law or are acts of persons acting on behalf of customary law. This case is one example of the imperfection of law due to the lack of strong fundamentals in the law. The imperfection of this law is real so that our view of seeing the law must be changed. Law must be seen as an art in interpreting an event. The incident that occurred in the Baduy community must be questioned related to the applicable customary law. The incident was a violation under Indonesian national law. The state recognizes the existence of customary law and respects the existence of customary law unless the customary law does not contradict with Indonesian national law.

In this case, many actions from customary law actually deviate from Indonesian criminal law. Explanation of Article 2 paragraph (1) of the new Criminal Code classifies customary law actions that deviate from criminal law to be called customary crimes and will be a new offense called customary offense. These things must be harmonized with national law so that it is in accordance with the objectives of Indonesian law itself. Every conflict that occurs in customary law must be straightened out through new legal mechanisms that can create prosperity in social life so that the law can be properly protected. It has become the role of the state in regulating all conflicts that occur within the customary law community so that they do not conflict with Indonesian law. The state needs to thoroughly review every customary law that applies in Indonesia so that it does not conflict with Indonesian law. The state must be able to create dialogue with indigenous and tribal peoples in order to reach an agreement to harmonize customary law with Indonesian criminal law. The problem of being able to review whether a customary law applies or not is very difficult because the unwritten nature of customary law causes doubts from Indonesian laws and regulations regarding actions in the form of customary sanctions applied by indigenous peoples. From this, the implementation of the internalization of customary law in Indonesian criminal law can be better and the regulation regarding customary law that is contrary to Indonesian law can be realized.

¹⁰ Acep Nazmudin, "Langgar Aturan Adat, Warga Baduy Bakar 4 Sepeda Motor, Videonya Viral di Medsos". <https://regional.kompas.com/read/2021/07/04/113928878/langgar-aturan-adat-warga-baduy-bakar-4-sepeda-motor-videonya-viral-di?page=all> (accessed November, 11 2022)

2. Problem Formulation

This study discusses how to apply the principle of legality to some customary law and finds out that the principle of legality will answer the settlement of customary law that conflicts with national law, and discusses how the process of harmonizing customary law is in the internalization process and knowing the process of harmonizing customary law in the internalization process so that it can determine behavior contrary to criminal law.

3. Research Methods

In conducting research, the selection and use of appropriate methods have an important role in achieving a targeted goal. The type of research method used in this journal belongs to normative legal research. Normative legal research is carried out by examining literature or secondary data based on the concepts of legal doctrines, norms, and regulations related to the issues discussed. Then, the approach used in this study is a qualitative approach. The qualitative approach itself is defined as a research that uses a scientific background with the aim of interpreting the phenomena that occur and is also carried out by involving various existing methods. The data and/or information processing technique applied by the Writing Team is a descriptive technique by conducting literature studies of scientific books and journals. Literature study is a series of activities related to methods of collecting library data, reading and taking notes, and processing research materials. As for supporting the substance of this scientific article, information is needed through data collection techniques. The writing team carried out data collection techniques based on secondary data. Secondary data is data that is already available and collected in various forms, including: laws and regulations, books, journals, as well as official and credible websites that support the writing of this scientific article.

B. DISCUSSION

1. INTERNALIZATION LIVING LAW IN INDONESIAN CRIMINAL LAW

There are two legal theories that are used to be able to underlie the writing of this paper, namely, the theory of dignified justice and the theory of legal certainty. The theory of dignified justice provides a view that law must be able to humanize humans.

Pancasila is the basis used in the theory of dignified justice because Pancasila is considered to have perfection to be able to create prosperity and peace in people's lives.¹¹

The theory of legal certainty exists to be able to provide justice for all legal subjects. Positive law must always be obeyed and must not be violated. The law must act firmly and not discriminate against any legal subject. Gustav Radbruch himself also believes that with the theory of legal certainty, the purpose of law in creating justice, benefit and certainty will be well realized.¹²

The statements that have been presented through the background section have generated some urgency to be able to internalize the living law into Indonesian criminal law. Some of the things that will later be stated as urgency in writing this paper are intended to be able to achieve justice, certainty, and legal benefits for the people of Indonesia, especially indigenous peoples. So from this, an explanation of the urgency in this paper is presented through several sections, each section will explain each part in a structured manner both from the problem, urgency, and resolution.

a. The Urgency of Applying Legality Principles to Customary Law

Hans Kelsen said that the meaning of justice is legality, which means that a general regulation is fair if it is applied in accordance with the written rules that regulate it with the aim of legitimizing law within government power in order to create an ideal rule of law state.¹³ The principle of legality is explicitly regulated in Article 1 paragraph (1) of the new Criminal Code stipulates that,

"No act may be subject to criminal sanctions and/or action except under the force of criminal regulations in existing laws and regulations before the act is committed."

This article explains that without written rules, a violation of an act cannot be punished. According to a Professor Jan Remmelink in his book *"Komentar atas Pasal-pasal terpenting dalam KUHP Belanda dan Padanannya dalam KUHP Indonesia"* or entitled in english *"Comments on the most important articles in the Dutch Criminal Code and their*

¹¹Teguh Prasetyo, *Keadilan Bermartabat Perspektif Teori Hukum*. Bandung: Nusa Media, Cetakan Kedua, 2015.

¹²Gustav Radbruch, *Tujuan Hukum*. Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama, 2012.

¹³ Uno Dua. "Perbandingan Asas Legalitas Menurut KUHP" *Academica*. https://www.academia.edu/4978927/PERBANDINGAN_ASAS_LEGALITAS_MENURUT_KUHP (accessed November 7, 2022)

equivalents in the Indonesian Criminal Code”, there are three things as the meaning contained in the principle of legality based on the view of Professor Jan Remmelink.¹⁴ First, regarding the concept of legislation contained in Article 1 paragraph (1) of the Criminal Code, according to Remmelink, the provision of punishment does not only speak of formal law, but includes all legislative products, both formal and material, which have legal legitimacy, including regulations made by local governments. Both at the provincial and district or city levels. Second, the formulated law must be detailed and accurate (*lex certa*). The formulation of criminal provisions that are unclear or too complicated will only create legal uncertainty and hinder the law enforcement process. Third, is a matter of analogy. The principle of legality also prohibits setting criminal provisions using an analogy known as an adage "*nullum crimen nulla poena sine lege stricta*."¹⁵ With the principle of legality, the purpose of law to be able to create justice, benefit and certainty in law will be well realized.

b. Review of Legal Cases Contrary to Criminal Law

Law is actually one thing that cannot be separated from the existence of society, so discussions about law will certainly go hand in hand with this discussion of society. Laws can be created when there are two or more humans in the environment. If there is only one human being then the law is irrelevant to apply because it has become the essence of the law itself which becomes a tool to be able to discipline society.¹⁶ Criminal law must be able to accommodate the principle of *lex certa* and *lex stricta* which in essence is a criminal offense must have clarity and firmness.¹⁷ Clarity and certainty in law can only be obtained by applying principles of *lex scripta* which means the law must be written. Meanwhile, customary law, which has an unwritten nature, does not have this principle, so many of these things are regulations in customary law in the criminal realm becomes unclear and even deviates from the application of criminal law.

¹⁴Jan Remmelink, *Hukum Pidana: Komentar atas Pasal-pasal terpenting dalam Kitab Undang- Undang Hukum Pidana Belanda dan Padanannya dalam Kitab Undang- Undang Hukum Pidana Indonesia* . Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama, 2003.

¹⁵ Iskandar, Bimo Prasetyo, "Inilah Pengertian Asas Legalitas di Kacamata Para Ahli Hukum".<https://bplawyers.co.id/2017/08/08/inilah-pengertian-asas-legalitas-di-kaca-mata-para-ahli-hukum/> (accessed November 5, 2022)

¹⁶Soerjono Soekanto, *Hukum Adat Indonesia*. Jakarta : RajaGrafindo Persada, 2008.

¹⁷Tongat, Said Noor Prasetyo, Nu'man Aunuh, Yaris Adhial Fajrin, "Hukum yang Hidup dalam Masyarakat dalam Pembaharuan Hukum Pidana Nasional", *Jurnal Living Law*, (2019)

Criminal law or public law regulates the interests of the public (people) with the authorities (state). The position of the ruler is a position that is higher than the position of the people.¹⁸ Because of this, the state has full authority over the implementation of criminal law to promote public welfare.

Criminal law has two main functions, namely general functions and special functions. The general function of criminal law is as a tool that can regulate people's lives. Andi Hamzah, in his book "*Asas-asas Hukum Pidana*" or entitled in English "*Principles of Criminal Law*" explained that criminal law is a nation's moral code, in this case it can be seen what exactly is prohibited to do in the life of a society.¹⁹ Then, the special function of criminal law is to protect legal interests against disgraceful acts. According to Satochid Kartanegara in his book "*Hukum Pidana*" or entitled in English "*Criminal law*" and Hermien Hadiati Koeswadji, in his book "*Perkembangan Macam-macam Pidana Rangka Pembangunan Hukum Pidana*" or entitled in English "*The Development of Various Criminal Laws in the Context of Development of Criminal Law*", there are five kinds of what is meant with regard to legal interests, namely: human life, human body or bodies, a person's honor, a person's independence, and property (theft).²⁰ Thus, criminal law should protect the community in order to achieve general welfare.

Customary law is a law that lives in a certain area or area according to its own nature. Although in general customary law is unwritten law, the state recognizes and respects the existence of customary law. In this case the meaning of the state respecting the existence of customary law does not mean that the state is subject to customary law, but rather as a form of the state to preserve the culture that existed even before the Indonesian state was formed. Customary law has a position that can be said to be the same as national law, but the existence of customary law must not conflict with applicable national law. However, if you look deeper, there are still problems related to the existence of customary law that contradicts the law, so this needs to be addressed and given further attention by the government.

In its application, customary law has many conflicts with criminal law in the life of the nation and state in Indonesia. This can be seen from the many actions that are

¹⁸Suyanto, *Pengantar Hukum Pidana*. Yogyakarta: Deepublish, 2018.

¹⁹ Ibid

²⁰ Ibid

contrary to the norms and laws and regulations in Indonesia. In fact, this action originating from customary law must be questioned and its validity reviewed, one example is the “*Kawin Tangkap*” tradition which is still valid in the Sumba area today even though this has been considered contrary to Indonesian criminal law.²¹ *Kawin Tangkap* is a tradition of marriage in Sumba area that requires a woman to be arrested by several men and taken to a place to propose a marriage. The woman would not know when she would be arrested and the arrestment of the woman would be sudden. Many of the women who were arrested suffered injuries as a result of resistance when defending themselves due to the sudden process of *Kawin Tangkap*. This tradition has been opposed by many people because it contradicts Article 328 of the Criminal Code concerning kidnapping.²² It is this customary law that is still valid that must be straightened out because it cannot conflict with applicable criminal law.

The unwritten nature of customary law raises the next problem, namely the actions of unscrupulous members of the customary law community who act on behalf of customary law to take arbitrary actions. This is because the unwritten nature of customary law makes it difficult to determine the applicability of the customary law itself so that it can be misused by arbitrary actions. For example, in the case of the burning of four motorbikes in the border area between the Inner Baduy and Outer Baduy. The burning was carried out by the Inner Baduy people who do not like outside culture entering the Inner Baduy area.²³ This action violated Article 187 of the Criminal Code concerning the crime of arson. Actions like this require further review whether the actions of the Baduy Dalam community are actions that are in accordance with the customary law that applies to the area or are anarchic actions in the name of customary law even though this is a form of rejection by certain individuals. Criminal law must be able to become a basis for customary law that applies in each region. The actions taken

²¹ Rachmawati, “Kisah-kisah Kawin Tangkap di Sumba, dari Alasan Nama Baik hingga Tuntutan Adat”. <https://regional.kompas.com/read/2022/08/02/094000378/kisah-kisah-kawin-tangkap-di-sumba-dari-alasan-nama-baik-hingga-tuntutan?page=all> (accessed November,11 2022)

²²Yogie Libra Fahlevi, “Perlindungan Hukum Terhadap Anak di Bawah Umur yang Dijadikan Objek Penculikan Menurut Kitab Undang-Undang Hukum Pidana”,*Skripsi* (Agustus 2020)

²³ Acep Nazmudin, “Langgar Aturan Adat, Warga Baduy Bakar 4 Sepeda Motor, Videonya Viral di Medsos”. <https://regional.kompas.com/read/2021/07/04/113928878/langgar-aturan-adat-warga-baduy-bakar-4-sepeda-motor-videonya-viral-di?page=all> (accessed November, 11 2022)

by these customary law communities must also be properly regulated in order to maintain order and peace in the area. In this case, the true role of the state is not to eliminate customary law that applies to every region in Indonesia. The state seeks to rectify customary law or customary actions that conflict with the law itself. Criminal law must be able to become a basis for customary law that applies in each region.

The law must be able to provide justice, benefit, and also certainty in society. In this case, the fulfillment of these three elements can be done by internalizing customary law in Indonesian criminal law to answer existing problems. The principle of legality must be applicable to some traditions of customary law that conflict with Indonesian criminal law. This is one of the efforts to make customary law more advanced and modern in keeping with the dynamics that occur in the surrounding environment and so that it does not conflict with national law.

c. Application of Legality Principles to Customary Law

Moeljatno said earlier that in ancient Rome there was a term known *crimine extra ordinaria*, namely crimes that are not regulated in statutory regulations. In doctrine *crimine extra ordinaria* by a term named *crimen stellionatus* which means evil or evil deeds. In the Middle Ages, when Ancient Roman law was applied and accepted on the Continent, many rulers, especially kings and queens, arbitrarily abused unwritten penal laws to achieve personal wishes.²⁴ Therefore, there are things that must be realized that every action that violates unwritten law deserves to be questioned whether the action given is a sanction as a result of being against the law or an action for personal gain in the name of law.

crimine extra ordinaria will only create legal uncertainty as happened in medieval Europe. Hans Kelsen through his theory namely, *Stufenbau Theory* or ladder theory suggests that a country's legislation is arranged like a pyramid with *grundnorm* (basic norms) which form the basis of the basis of the law itself.²⁵ Article 1 paragraph (1) of the new Criminal Code determines that,

*"No one can be punished or subject to action, unless the act committed has been determined as a criminal offense in the laws and regulations that were in effect at the time the act was committed."*²⁶

²⁴Eddy O.s Hiariej, *Asas Legalitas dan Penemuan Hukum dalam Hukum Pidana*. Jakarta: Erlangga, 2009.

²⁵ Op.Cit 6

²⁶ Tarmizi, *KUHAP and KUHP* (East Jakarta: Editors of Sinar Graphic, 2021), 3.

The statement explicitly explains that the principle of legality is a must in Indonesian criminal law so that all violations and crimes in customary law are contained in a written regulation. The application of the principle of legality requires the internalization of customary law in criminal law in order to create legal certainty itself.

The form of customary law as living law experienced a lot of conflict with Indonesian criminal law as it has been explained that the unwritten form of customary law raises problems in terms of arbitrary actions or actions that deviate from actions from Indonesian national law. The application of the legality principle is a powerful solution to overcome these problems. It must be emphasized here, that what is regulated is the actions of customary law or the actions of customary law communities that deviate from Indonesian criminal law so that not all customary law will be applied to the principle of legality in it. The application of the principle of legality will focus on actions from customary law relating to deviations from criminal law or also known as customary crimes.

In Article 2 paragraph (3) of the new Criminal Code it is written,

"Provisions regarding procedures and criteria for establishing laws that live in society are regulated by government regulation."

Later, Indonesian government regulation is required to regulate related arrangements living law which must be regulated through regional regulations that occur in their respective districts.²⁷ Customary law is internalized through local regulation, because regions know more about matters related to culture and customary law in their respective regions. Regional governments through regional autonomy will be tasked with being able to carry out dialogues between regional governments and customs in their regions so that they can reach an agreement where there will be special regulations regarding criminal acts specifically through regional regulations. Violations or criminal crimes committed by indigenous and tribal peoples will provide new offenses in the Indonesian criminal system, namely, customary offenses. The definition of customary offenses has been explained through the elucidation of Article 2 paragraph (1) of the new Criminal Code.²⁸

²⁷ "Draft Law 2022 BOOK OF CRIMINAL LAWS"
hukumonline.com<https://www.hukumonline.com/pusatdata/detail/17797/rancangan-undang-undang-2019> (accesed November,11 2022)

²⁸ Ibid.

The internalization process will eliminate the nature of customary law as living law unwritten, dynamic, flexible and also discriminatory through the implementation of customary law in Indonesian criminal law. Local regulations that have been formed through the internalization of customary law in criminal law will also provide regulations that will be closely related to customary law provisions. This is because the resulting regional regulations are the legal form of all agreements to rectify customary law in one law. This internalization will only reduce the unwritten nature of customary law and also eliminate uncertainty in the customary law itself. Other principles of customary law, such as the principle of kinship, the principle of mutual assistance, and the principle of social function, are still present in the application of regional regulations which are the unification of every existing customary law in the area.²⁹ The application of sanctions in regional regulations will be prioritized by using customary elements in accordance with the agreement between the regional government and elders from the local customary law community. The governing regional regulations will also provide equality for all indigenous and tribal peoples in related laws so that from this, there is no discriminatory nature that determines a gender and where the community comes from. All indigenous and tribal peoples will be called legal subjects of a country and will have the same similarities in the eyes of criminal law. This internalization also aims to be able to provide relief for accidents and acts of self-defense that were previously ignored by customary law. The dynamic and flexible nature of customary law will also disappear because there is already written legal certainty through regional regulations. The dynamic nature of customary law actually gives uncertainty to the law itself because most of customary law has an unwritten nature and is easy to change with the times. This dynamism and unwritten law can be used by elements in carrying out deviant individual actions in the name of local customary law.

This internalization process has a noble purpose in order to create prosperity within the community. The purpose of law in the form of providing justice, benefit, and also certainty in law will make society more prosperous. Some customary law as living law has deviated from Indonesian criminal law, it must be straightened out by granting the principle of legality. The application of the principle of legality will be a good key to rectifying and re-enforcing the law in Indonesia so that it conforms to the constitution and ideology of the Indonesian state.

²⁹ Dr. St. Laksanto Utomo, *Customary law* (Depok: Rajawali Press, 2017), 9.

2. The Process of Harmonizing Customary Laws in the Internalization Process

The unwritten nature of customary law causes the weakness of legal certainty presented in it. With this weak certainty, there are certain individuals who can abuse the nature of the unwritten law. So from this, the internalization process into a national regulation is the right way to be able to bring justice, benefit, and certainty to the laws that live in society.

a. Overview of the Process of Harmonizing Customary Law with Criminal Law

The process of internalizing customary law into criminal law is a good process, because it incorporates the positive values contained in every custom in Indonesia into criminal law laws. However, in reality, not all matters regulated in customary law are good. Referring to the facts in the previous discussion, it shows that there are still many customary laws in force that conflict with national law, so that it becomes an urgency that must be addressed immediately. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out an alignment process on customary law to ensure that customary law does not conflict with national law.

Alignment in the Big Indonesian Dictionary is a process, way, act of aligning; adjustment. The alignment process, in this case, is necessary so that the process of internalizing customary law values can run effectively and not conflict with criminal law. In addition, this process is also to ensure that customary law which is internalized into criminal law through local regulations does not contradict or deviate from the criminal law above it. Alignment can be done by conducting a thorough review of every customary law in Indonesia so that it does not deviate from Indonesian criminal law, as well as knowing whether the action is purely based on the provisions of said customary law, or the action is only an act of an individual acting on behalf of customary law.

Indonesian Law number 12 of 2011 concerning the Establishment of Legislation explains that the community has the right to provide input verbally or in writing in the form of seminars, workshops and discussions.³⁰ In accordance with this law, local governments can provide containers in the form of focus group discussion to conduct negotiations between the local government and each customary elder who is the representative of the customary law community in each of the customary tribes in the area, to discuss each other's customary customs and negotiate to carry out legal unification. Legal unification here aims to improve the actions of customary law or the

³⁰ Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 12 of 2011 concerning the Formation of Legislation

actions of individuals acting on behalf of customary law that deviate or conflict with criminal law and include them in regional regulations.

In the life of a nation, of course we want certainty, benefit, and justice. Therefore, it is necessary to establish a law in the form of a regional regulation to overcome problems arising from customary laws that conflict with applicable national law. In addition to this, the establishment of regional regulations to adjust customary law with national law can minimize the misuse of customary law by parties because recognized customary law will apply as written law.

b. Implementation of Settlement of Customary Crimes After Internalizing Customary Law into Criminal Law

After the application of the legality principle and the alignment process, there is a need for a new application in balancing customary values and national legal values in creating justice. There will be the addition of a new system in solving problems in the customary environment. This new system is in the form of the creation of a special institution that becomes a forum for giving social views which is simultaneously required to be formed in every customary environment in every region.

According to Article 1 paragraph (8) of the Indigenous Law Community Bill states that,

"Customary Institutions are instruments that have the authority to regulate, manage, and resolve various life problems based on customs and customary law, which have grown and developed together with the history of Indigenous Peoples."

³¹

According to the bill, in fact all customary issues will be resolved and determined according to the decision of the local customary institution. The function of customary institutions in the Indigenous Peoples Bill has a similar function to the customary court which was removed through Presidential Decree number 6 of 1966.³² The innovation of forming traditional institutions is actually a good step not to solve problems but rather as a social forum. Article 103 letter e of the Village Law explains that there is a customary village court peace trial which functions to resolve problems peacefully.³³ The related articles in the Customary Law Society Bill and the Village Law will be used in the

³¹ Op.Cit.

³² Regulation of the President of the Republic of Indonesia No. 6 of 1966 concerning the abolition of customary/self-governing courts and the establishment of district courts in West Irian.

³³ Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 6 of 2014 concerning Villages.

development of a new system for solving problems in the customary environment. After this internalization, any actions of indigenous and tribal peoples that conflict with national criminal law will be resolved by means of a new system which will later be formed through local regulations. The role of customary institutions previously described in the Customary Law Society Bill will relinquish the role of problem solving. This also changes the article of the Village Law on customary village justice, which refers to the role of customary institutions as customary village courts. Here there will be a separation between customary institutions and also customary village courts. Customary institutions will later play the role of representing customary law communities by providing studies on issues related to customary law in customary village courts, in which case customary institutions will be specifically known as *amicus curiae* or in english as friends of the court.³⁴ Then, a traditional village justice institution will be formed which will stand alone to be able to resolve any problems that occur in the customary environment which in terms of settlement will be based on local regulations.

In the world of courts that use the legal system common law, Certain parties that are not directly related to parties related to existing problems can provide knowledge to judges through their views.³⁵

The party that gave knowledge to the judge is named *amicus curiae*. Even though Indonesia has a different legal system, the implementation of *amicus curiae* applicable that has placement outside the Indonesian court proceedings. In the Indonesian court system which adheres to the system civil law, *amicus curiae* is used implicitly with a different name that is a friend of the court.³⁶ Article 184 paragraph (1) The Indonesian Criminal Procedure Code regarding evidence in court, there is no list of *amicus curiae*.³⁷ *Amicus curiae* can be submitted by anyone by members of customary institutions who follow the development of existing customary criminal cases so that from this, *amicus curiae* are differences between witnesses and expert testimony in court.³⁸ *Amicus curiae*

³⁴ Sarah Williams, Hannah Woolaver, Emma Palmer, *The Amicus Curiae in International Criminal Justice*, Hart Publishing, 2020.

³⁵ Linda Ayu Pralampita, "Kedudukan Amicus Curiae Dalam Sistem Peradilan di Indonesia," *LEX Renaissance* 5, NO. 3 (JULI 2020)

³⁶ Ibid.

³⁷ Anak Agung Gde Rahmadi, "Amicus Curiae dalam Pembuktian Perkara Pidana di Pengadilan," *Jurnal Kertha Semaya* 9, No. 2 (2021)

³⁸ Linda Ayu Pralampita, Loc.cit.

does not provide information for the purposes of investigation, prosecution and trial regarding a criminal case that he himself heard, saw for himself, and experienced for himself. These things are the role of the witness in the court stages because it is the role of the witness which is clearly written in Article 1 paragraph (26) of the Criminal Procedure Code.³⁹ *Amicus curiae* also cannot be said to be an expert witness because an expert witness is required by a person who has special expertise to explain issues as stated in Article 1 paragraph (28) of the Criminal Procedure Code.⁴⁰ *Amicus curiae* doesn't have to be an expert or someone who directly sees, feels, and is in it but, *amicus curiae* can be done by anyone and will provide clarification of the actual issues that exist, explain existing legal issues, and represent certain groups, all of which are intended to provide additional knowledge to judges in exploring and resolving this criminal case.

From the previous paragraph, it has been explained about the relationship between courts which refers to general courts and also *amicus curiae* if reviewed on the limits set in the regional regulations which only provide a maximum penalty in the form of confinement, all of which are executed by the Civil Service Police Unit, then this becomes irrelevant to the topics and innovations discussed in this paper because the execution committed by the Civil Service Police Unit cannot enter the court. The new system to be formed will involve roles of *amicus curiae* which will later be played by traditional institutions and will be included in the customary village justice structure itself. So from this, the resolution of customary problems in accordance with regulations that have been regulated through regional regulations cannot enter the general court but through the customary village court. However, if the customary village court cannot resolve the problems that occur, the case will be transferred to the general court and the basis used later will not use regional regulations but use laws that are above regional regulations.

The function of customary institutions is as a place to be *amicus curiae* representing each custom in the customary village court. Application *amicus curiae* through customary institutions is a form of respect for the customary law community itself. Existence *amicus curiae* in Indonesia actually does not have a clear legal force. Referring to that, *amicus curiae* needs to be regulated in general in government

³⁹ Law No. 8 of 1981 dated December 31, 1981 concerning Criminal Procedure Code.

⁴⁰ Ibid

regulation which will later be formed in order to provide legal certainty for its existence in Indonesia, especially its application to customary institutions and customary village courts. The government regulation later, must explain in general in the article regarding the formation of customary institutions in each customary law community and the role of customary institutions as *amicus curiae* in cases of customary offenses. The government regulation that will be formed, must also regulate the formation of regional regulations in each region in Indonesia to explain in general about solving customary offenses that must be resolved with the new system that will be formed.

C. Conclusion

Based on the discussion above, it is interesting that the Writing Team has drawn conclusions regarding the legal discussion in this paper. First, the implementation of some actions originating from customary law has deviations from criminal law as one of Indonesia's national laws. The unwritten nature of customary law has also led to the emergence of elements who act arbitrarily in the name of customary law. These things gave rise to an urgency to internalize some customary law in criminal law in order to create justice, benefit and certainty as stated in Article 2 paragraph (1) of the new Criminal Code. The existence of customary law has the same position as Indonesian national law, however, customary law may not conflict with Indonesian national law as written in Article 18B paragraph (2) of the 1945 Constitution.

Second, Departing from the urgency that has been described, the Writing Team provides an idea to insert friends of the court (*amicus curiae*) which is specifically carried out by traditional institutions which will later be formed to be able to provide views in the customary village court which will stand apart from traditional institutions. Support from the mechanism that the Writing Team proposes is also in line with the theory of dignified justice which states that in order to achieve laws that humanize humans based on Pancasila. This idea also departs from Gustav Radbruch's theory of legal certainty which implies legal certainty that the ideal law is a positive law, not easily changed, based on facts to avoid mistakes that are clearly contrary to pure customary law. Therefore, if our proposals are accepted, then surely national development, especially human development, can be fulfilled.

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